

STUDIES IN THE BEHAVIOUR OF BI-UNIVALENT SALTS IN AQUEOUS SOLUTION. PART I. LEAD NITRATE

BY S. NATH, S. ADITYA AND B. PRASAD

The R.M.F. of the following types of the cell

where Pb_xHg_y represents a two phase amalgam of Pb and Hg were studied at a number of concentrations of lead nitrate. These experiments show that lead nitrate is completely dissociated in dilute aqueous solutions up to 0.05 molar. Transport number of Pb^{++} in lead nitrate has also been calculated at a number of concentrations by studies of the cell of the second kind.

Barium chloride amongst the bi-univalent electrolytes has the greatest probability of complete dissociation. The comparison of the plots of (a) Ω (equivalent conductance) against $\sqrt{C}$, and (b) conductance ratio Ω/Ω_x against C , of lead nitrate with the corresponding plots of barium chloride leads one to suspect that lead nitrate may not be completely dissociated. The dissociation of lead nitrate has been studied by Davies (*Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1927, 23, 354; 1930, 26, 592) by conductance methods. He has computed the dissociation constant of PbNO_3^+ , $\rightleftharpoons \text{Pb}^{++} + \text{NO}_3^-$, to be 6.47×10^{-2} . He has worked on certain assumptions as to the standard behaviour of the bi-univalent salts. He has used various methods of approximations, a review of which is given by Harned and Owen ("Physical Chemistry of Electrolytic Solutions"). It was considered worthwhile to examine Davies' interpretation from the potentiometric measurements.

The cells of the type :

were studied.

In such a study liquid junction comes in. But it has been found that the liquid junction potential in the case of saturated NH_4NO_3 or KCl bridge is nearly eliminated. Several experiments on calomel concentration cells using HCl and a chloride on the two sides with liquid junction of KCl or NH_4NO_3 were also performed. Our observations show that the liquid junction potential with saturated KCl or NH_4NO_3 bridge is never more than one millivolt. As KCl could not be used NH_4NO_3 bridge was adopted. It was shown by Puschin (*Z. anorg. Chem.*, 1903, 36, 201) that all lead amalgams having a percentage of lead, between 1.8 and 66 exhibited the same electromotive force. Henderson and Stegeman (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1918, 40, 84) confirmed the results between 2.5% and 6%. These results also follow from the phase diagram of the system lead and mercury, as it is found that for the above mentioned percentages the system is a two-phase amalgam in which the composition of both the phases is fixed. So lead amalgam of about 4% was used. Cells of the type

were also studied to throw light on the nature of $\text{Pb}(\text{NO}_3)_2$ in solution.

E X P E R I M E N T A L

Analar quality lead nitrate was recrystallised and analysed. The amount of lead found was 99.8% of the theoretical value. The amalgam was prepared by electrolysing 10% (g./100 c. c.) lead nitrate solution with redistilled mercury cathode and platinum anode. In order to avoid lead peroxide formed at the anode falling on the amalgam, the anode and cathode compartments consisting of beakers containing the lead nitrate solution were joined together by an inverted U tube containing the same solution. The electrolysis was continued till the lead liberated at the cathode was about 4% (3.81% by actual analysis) of the mercury taken at the cathode. The amalgam was washed, dried and kept in a flask in an atmosphere of carbon dioxide. At a temperature above 60° the amalgam became an one-phase system. It was transferred to half cells in carbon dioxide atmosphere by heating it on a water-bath. On cooling to room temperature it became a two-phase amalgam once again. The solutions were put in the half cells after the amalgam and the solutions were replaced once or twice to be sure that correct equilibrium had been attained. The bridge used was of the type used by Guggenheim (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1930, **52**, 1311). The U tube and its stopper had the same diameter i. e. 3 mm. The entire assembly with bridge is shown in Figure 1. Each experiment was done in duplicate and the duplicates agreed within 0.2 mv. For

Fig. 1

performing duplicate experiments four half cells were required, two of which had the same composition. These half cells having the same composition were always checked against each other by joining them together with a rubber tube containing the same solution and seeing that the E. M. F. developed was not more than 0.2 mv. The temperature was noted in each case and E. M. F. was converted to 25° by using

$$\frac{E_1}{E_2} = \frac{T_1}{T_2}$$

For the study of the cells of the type,

the half cells were filled as in the other case. They were joined together by U tubes containing the solution of the higher concentration. Even, when joined by a beaker containing solutions of the higher concentration the readings were the same.

TABLE I

Conc.	R.M.F. (obs.).	Temp.	E.M.F. (obs.) converted to 25°.	* E.M.F. (calc.) at 25°.	E (obs.) - E (calc.).
0.01-0.02	0.00628 volt	27.0°	0.00624 volt	0.00613	0.1m.volt
0.01-0.03	0.00970	26.7°	0.00964	0.00904	0.6
0.01-0.04	0.01170	26.7°	0.01163	0.01116	0.5
0.01-0.05	0.01343	27.5°	0.01332	0.01251	0.8
0.01-0.06	0.01470	27.8°	0.01456	0.01339	1.2
0.005-0.01	0.00723	24.7°	0.00724	0.00627	1.0
0.005-0.02	0.01365	23.9°	0.01370	0.01240	1.3
0.005-0.03	0.01660	23.4°	0.01669	0.01531	1.3
0.005-0.04	0.01890	24.3°	0.01895	0.01743	1.5
0.005-0.05	0.02078	25.6°	0.02075	0.01876	2.0
0.005-0.06	0.02170	27.6°	0.02152	0.01965	1.9
0.02-0.03	0.00325	24.3°	0.00326	0.00291	0.3
0.02-0.04	0.00510	24.4°	0.00511	0.00503	0.1
0.02-0.05	0.00700	25.2°	0.00699	0.00638	0.6
0.02-0.06	0.00795	24.5°	0.00796	0.00726	0.7
0.03-0.05	0.00380	25.0°	0.00380	0.00347	0.3
0.03-0.06	0.00470	25.0°	0.00470	0.00435	0.3
0.04-0.06	0.00280	25.1°	0.00289	0.00223	0.6
0.002-0.005	0.01055	22.9°	0.01062	0.00887	1.7

* Calc. from $E = \frac{RT}{2F} \log \frac{C_1^{21}}{C_2^{72}}$.

TABLE II

Concentration. (1)	(2)	R.M.F. (obs.).	Temp.	R.M.F. (obs.) converted to 25°.	* E.M.F. (calc.).
0.01	0.02	0.01130 volt	27.0°	0.01125	0.01069
0.01	0.03	0.01760	27.0°	0.01748	0.01650
0.01	0.04	0.02200	26.2°	0.02191	0.02045
0.01	0.05	0.02593	26.9°	0.02576	0.02345
0.01	0.06	0.02830	27.6°	0.02804	0.02583
0.005	0.01	0.01235	24.8°	0.01236	0.01138
0.005	0.02	0.02405	24.0°	0.02413	0.02206
0.005	0.03	0.02080	23.9°	0.02090	0.02789
0.005	0.04	0.03280	24.4°	0.03291	0.03184
0.005	0.05	0.03790	26.0°	0.03777	0.03483
0.005	0.06	0.04000	26.5°	0.03980	0.03722
0.02	0.03	0.00625	24.3°	0.00626	0.00583
0.02	0.04	0.01015	23.8°	0.01019	0.00978
0.02	0.05	0.01340	24.1°	0.01344	0.01277
0.02	0.06	0.01580	24.9°	0.01581	0.01516
0.03	0.05	0.00755	25.0°	0.00755	0.00695
0.03	0.06	0.00975	25.0°	0.00975	0.00933
0.04	0.06	0.00585	24.5°	0.00586	0.00538
0.002	0.005	0.01670	23.1°	0.01681	0.01572

* Calc. from $E = \frac{3}{2} \frac{RT}{F} \log \frac{a_1\text{Pb}(\text{NO}_3)_2}{a_2\text{Pb}(\text{NO}_3)_2}$

DISCUSSION

The E. M. F. of the cells of the type
 $\text{Hg}_2\text{Pb}_x \mid \text{Pb}(\text{NO}_3)_2 \mid \text{Pb}(\text{NO}_3)_2 \mid \text{Hg}_2\text{Pb}_x$ at 25° are given in Table I.

The E. M. F. of the cell can be represented by the equation

$$E = \frac{RT}{2F} \log \frac{C_1 \gamma_1}{C_2 \gamma_2}$$

where C_1 and C_2 and γ_1 and γ_2 are the concentrations and the activity coefficients of the Pb^{++} ions in the two solutions. The activity coefficient of the Pb^{++} ions will not change with temperature as solutions of lead salt at the concentrations used will behave like semi-ideal solutions, where no change takes place in the activity coefficient due to change in temperature. Now, to calculate the E. M. F. it is required to know the activity of the Pb^{++} ions in solution. The activity of Pb^{++} has been calculated from the knowledge of the activity coefficient of $\text{Pb}(\text{NO}_3)_2$, KNO_3 and KCl (given in Landolt, Bronstein, Roth and Scheel Tables) on the lines suggested by G. N. Lewis ("Thermodynamics", Lewis & Randall, 1923 Ed., Chapter XXVIII, p. 380). These calculated values of E. M. F. given in column 5 agree fairly well with those in column 4 when the concentrations on the two sides do not differ much. When the concentrations differ a great deal, the difference between the calculated and the observed values of E. M. F. also increases. This may be either due to the diffusion potential not being completely eliminated or due to the $\text{Pb}(\text{NO}_3)_2$ being almost completely, but not completely, dissociated in the solution, but the smallness of the difference shows even if the dissociation is not complete, it is almost complete.

The readings for the cells of the type

are given in Table II. The E. M. F. of the cell of the above type is represented by

$$E = \frac{3}{2} \cdot \frac{RT}{F} \log \frac{a_1 \text{Pb}(\text{NO}_3)_2}{a_2 \text{Pb}(\text{NO}_3)_2}$$

Here also, appreciable error will not be introduced in converting the observed E. M. F. to 25° by taking $E_1/E = T_1/T_2$.

The converted E. M. F. are given in column 4. Assuming the transport number from conductance data to be correct, the E. M. F. have been calculated. They are found to agree well with the observed ones within the experimental errors.

Following the method of MacInnes (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1920, **42**, 117) the transport number for Pb^{++} has been calculated from the E. M. F. data and the knowledge of activity coefficient of $\text{Pb}(\text{NO}_3)_2$ given in Landolt-Bornstein-Roth-Scheel Tables.

When complex formation takes place so that the simple cations in dilute solution become a part of the complex ions in the concentrated solutions or when stepwise dissociation takes place, the t_+ is found to change much more than it would change due to

the change in ionic conductance with concentration. The following table, containing the t_+ of $\text{Pb}(\text{NO}_3)_2$ (calculated by the method of MacInnes) and t_+ in CdI_2 , shows the contrast.

Cation transport number in CdI_2		Transport number of Pb^{++} in $\text{Pb}(\text{NO}_3)_2$	
Conc.	t_+	Conc.	t_+
0.005	0.445	0.020 (0.01/0.03)	0.465
0.01	0.444	0.030 (0.02/0.04)	0.4738
0.002	0.443	0.040 (0.03/0.05)	0.4511
0.05	0.396	0.050 (0.04/0.06)	0.4501
0.1	0.296		

From these observations it appears that lead nitrate is completely dissociated in the range of concentrations studied.

MAYURBHANJ CHEMICAL LABORATORY,
REVENSHAW COLLEGE, CUTTACK.

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